

Those holding the fort: The complexity of human mobility beyond traditional patterns

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Abstract. One-third of working families in the UK are estimated to have at least one parent outside the formal workforce, engaging in various household and caring activities both inside and outside the home. Understanding the local movement patterns of this group, as well as their relation to their urban environment and socio-economic reality, is fundamental to developing inclusive public policies promoting access to diverse and sustainable types of amenities. In this work, with the aim of mobile data records and different socioeconomic datasets, we propose building location-based travel diaries to explore such patterns.

Keywords. Human Mobility, mobile traces, complexity

1. Introduction

One-third of working families in the UK (Labour Market, 2021) are estimated to have at least one parent outside the formal workforce, engaging in various household and caring activities both inside and outside the home. In addition to this stay-at-home group, many office workers have adopted flexible working patterns since the COVID-19 pandemic. A recent survey (TfL, 2023) of Central London workers found that half of the respondents work in the office at least three days a week. These findings suggest that work is no longer the central activity shaping individuals' routines for a large percentage of London's population, as this flexibility allows for prioritising other activities such as well-being, childcare, and leisure. We argue that this is particularly evident at a local (neighbourhood) scale, an aspect that has been understudied at a large scale.

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Travel surveys have provided insights into the local scale of human mobility (Ampt et al. 2004). Although rich in details, they have imposed constraints on sample size and study areas. New data sources, like mobile phone records, have produced more accurate patterns. These can include primary (home-to-work) and secondary activities, including leisure, shopping, and chain trips.

Nevertheless, these mobility studies focus on modelling the flows or defining patterns in the traditional commuters' chain of activities. For instance, the home-school-work-lunch-work-groceries-home motif is a classic motif followed by thousands of workers in UK cities. But what about non-traditional working patterns? What about stay-at-home parents who balance taking younger kids to the park, getting groceries, picking up the older kids from school, and preparing meals?

The present study contributes to methodological efforts for inferring information on individuals from aggregate data. Using a spatial and temporally aggregated dataset from mobile phone apps usage for a month in the Greater London Area, we create location-based (Figure 1) travel diaries to analyse urban mobility while avoiding using sensitive data.

Figure 1. Non-9-to-5 workers carry out different activities in their neighbourhoods or the nearby vicinity. The nature of these activities is related to what is offered in the area, which, in cities such as London, is almost homogenous, i.e., there are eating, leisure and cultural amenities in almost all neighbourhoods. However, the brand or quality of service offered greatly varies depending on the socioeconomic and cultural characteristics of the area.

2. Data and Methods

The mobile data, provided by the company Locomizer (locomizer.com), is collected via various smartphone applications. The data is aggregated at Uber Hexagon level 8 in the Greater London Area (GLA), UK. We derive hourly Origin-Destination flows for June 2023 for each hexagon (Figure 2) and enhance them with Point of Interest data from OSM. First, we look at the spatial representation of this data aggregated by month, distinguishing between users classified as “9-5” workers and everybody else. In this research, we denominated the former “*work*” and the latter “*all*” and derived a descriptive statistics set for each group.

Figure 2. Aggregated flows in June 2023 per hexagon in the mobile data. The left panel shows the spatial distribution of flows at the Origin. This heterogeneous pattern corresponds with high-density residential areas. The right panel shows the Destination. At this large aggregation scale, the distribution of destination hexagons is driven by flows ending around the main public transport hubs and follows main road networks. Both maps' large empty or low-count areas correspond mostly with natural land uses where population density is low.

Once we obtain the OD flows, we build hourly travel diaries that follow the in-and-out flows per hexagon as follows:

Hexagon Travel diaries (HTd) algorithm

1. Prune traditional workers (9-5 flows).
2. Set frequency level n ($n=2$ in this document)
3. Select all the OD from a Hexagon **Hi** by day and time. These are raw diaries, as some flows could appear only once a month.
4. To extract daily patterns, we applied the Eclat level n mining algorithm (Zaki, 2000). This algorithm obtains hexagons that interact with **Hi** at least n times a month on the same day/hour, and the amount of this interaction.

After we obtain the HTd for **Hi**, we study the POIs inside **Hi** and derive different statistics:

- Number of visited Hexagons by day/hour
- Mean travelled distance/time
- Diversity of services (e.g. type of schools)
- Diversity of POIs (e.g. type of supermarket)

To relate the above measures to the underlying social and urban environment, we added two more characteristics to **Hi**: England's Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD,2019) and the UK's Standard Occupation Classification (SOC, Census,2021).

3. Data and Methods

These diaries tell a story in different parts of the city, capturing where people from different socio-economic and, to some extent, different cultural backgrounds move across the day.

First, we grouped the main SOC categories to understand the different occupations' spatio-temporal habits.

Layer 1: Occupations 1,2,3:

- Managers, directors.
- Professional
- Associate Professional

Layer 3: Occupations 7,8,9:

- Sales and customer service
- Process, plant and machine operatives
- Elementary occupations

Comparing both layers against some of the obtained flow statistics reveals occupation differences. Figure 3 shows an example of this difference for the average flows on Wednesdays in June 2023.

Figure 3. Observed differences between hexagons with occupations belonging to layer 1 vs layer 3. a) Average travelled distance from Origin hexagons to their pattern. Both patterns follow the traditional morning/afternoon peaks. However, the travelled distance from hexagons in layer 1 (OC1) is larger. The information packed in this plot is vast. For example, in the early/late hours, the distance travelled from OC1 (managers) is less than OC9 (Elementary occupations), signalling the profound differences in how these

groups behave. In terms of visited locations, both groups again follow the same trend of morning/afternoon activity, but the elementary location, on a Wednesday, visits fewer locations in general. Panels c and d show the distribution of travelled distance (c) and visited hexagons (d) throughout June 23.

Our preliminary results show that occupations in group L1 travel farthest and visit more amenities than those in group L3. However, group L3 travelled to far locations on average.

In other words, the professional and managerial sectors tend to travel to more places with diverse leisure and food options than sales representatives and cleaners.

When linking the hexagon travel diaries with the IMD and the POIS diversity, we uncover another aspect of the socioeconomic impact on local movements. For example, members from layers 1 or 3 can access Children's centres, parks, and shops in areas with high or low IMD. However, areas with a larger layer one population have higher accessibility to betting parlours and fast-food restaurants.

4. Conclusions and future work

Our initial results recover the typical working hexagon patterns but also show a correlation between hexagons with high indexes of multiple deprivations and particular moving patterns. The similarity in movement patterns shows the spatial correlation of areas with high IMD with types of fast-food places and leisure, like betting shops; In contrast, low IMD areas have access to a wide variety of food, retail and leisure centres during the day.

Future work includes formalising an identity score for each H_i based on its similar patterns to those of the other hexagons. The idea is to create a similarity field that informs how similar H_i is to H_j .

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